

Local Government in Switzerland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in Switzerland

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Types of Local Governments

The Swiss model of federalism, based on the principle of subsidiarity, is structured in three layers of political representation, i.e. the Confederation (national government), the cantons and the municipalities. The Constitution of the Swiss Confederation, however, focuses on two layers only, the national and cantonal. In its Article 1 it not only lists the official 26 cantons but also gives them constitutive effect. In Article 3 it sets the rules for the power-sharing arrangements between the Confederation and the cantons: ‘The Cantons are sovereign except to the extent that their sovereignty is limited by the Federal Constitution. They exercise all rights that are not vested in the Confederation.’ However, one must bear in mind that the term ‘competent’ would be more appropriate than ‘sovereign’ to describe the power vested in the cantons. In fact, the cantons have competence on all the tasks and duties that do not fall on the Confederation. But they nevertheless remain subdued to the Confederation, as the majority of the other cantons can impose their will on a canton via a revision of the Swiss Constitution. Indeed, according to the Article 48(a) of the Swiss Constitution, at the request of interested cantons, the Confederation may declare intercantonal agreements to be generally binding or require cantons to participate in intercantonal agreements in the following fields:

- the execution of criminal penalties and measures;
- school education in the matters specified in Article 62(4);
- cantonal institutions of higher education;
- cultural institutions of supra-regional importance; e. waste management;
- waste water treatment;
- urban transport;
- advanced medical science and specialist clinics;
- institutions for the rehabilitation and care of invalids.

The Federal Constitution does not attribute any competence to regulate local government to the national government. The municipalities are therefore created by and subjected to cantonal regulation. Thus, each canton defines the status and the competences of its municipalities in its cantonal constitution and legislation. We therefore differentiate 26 systems of municipalities corresponding to each of the 26 Swiss cantons. Still, one can identify five main types of municipalities:

- the classical political municipalities which are called *commune* in French, *comune* in Italian and *Gemeinde*, *Ortsgemeinde* or *Einwohnergemeinde* in German depending on the cantons. They are the basic general-purpose type of municipality;
- the so-called *bourgeoise* municipalities that have survived from the Middle Age in some cantons. When in 1798 the Helvetic Republic is proclaimed; the cantons are put on an equal footing and the inhabitants of the Swiss territory receive the Swiss citizenship. The original bourgeois do not agree to share the communal properties (lands, forests, etc.) with the new *bourgeoise*. Thus, the *bourgeoise* municipalities keep the control over the communal properties and the political municipalities guarantee the political rights to the new *bourgeoise*. As of today, in the cantons where such *bourgeoise* municipalities remain, they are mainly land owners and service providers (for example retirement houses, subsidized apartments, young offenders' facilities, etc.);
- the ecclesiastical community is the territorial division that is attached to a church and that is often called parish (*paroisse* in French). They are a single-purpose body;
- the so-called scholar commune *commune scolaire* is also a single-purpose body that deals with the school system on a certain territory within the limits assigned by the canton and that does not automatically match with the political municipality. For example, the school program remains a cantonal competence but the decision to build the school or to organize the carriage of school pupils is, to a large extent, delegated to the scholar municipalities;¹
- other types of municipalities that exist in some cantons.

Finally, one must add that the majority of the Swiss cantons have put in place an intermediary political level between the cantons and the municipalities called the district (*district* in French, *Bezirk*, *Verwaltungsregion*, *Verwaltungskreis*, *Wahlkreis*, *Amtei* or *Amt* in German, *distretto* in Italian). Out of the 26 cantons, only six do not have such a subdivision. These districts are very different from each other but they usually correspond to a group of municipalities. Again, the cantons hold the primary competence regarding their internal organization and scope.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The constitution framework that prevailed until 1999 did not mention municipalities, unless incidentally. Only the adoption of a new constitution that year ensured that local autonomy was granted constitutional protection.² Article 50 reads as follows: (i) 'The autonomy of the communes is guaranteed in accordance with cantonal law.'; (ii) 'The Confederation shall take account in its activities of the possible consequences for the communes.'; (iii) 'In doing so, it

¹ Nicolas Schmitt, *Local Government in Switzerland: Organisation and Competences* (forthcoming).

² Schmitt, *Local Government in Switzerland*, above.

shall take account of the special position of the cities and urban areas as well as the mountain regions.’

The effect of the new provision is limited. The extent of local autonomy remains in the hands of the cantons (‘in accordance with cantonal law’) and each of them thus continues to autonomously define its internal governance system. Only as far as cantonal law provides for municipal autonomy, it is guaranteed by the Federal Constitution. Consequently, municipal autonomy is justiciable and the Federal Supreme Court hears disputes concerning violations of it (Article 189(1)(e)). When it does so, it refers to the cantonal constitution and the cantonal legislative framework to determine the scope of local autonomy and decide whether the canton has impinged on it or not.

If the Article 50(2) of the Constitution constrains the Confederation, while fulfilling its tasks (e.g. military, national highways), to be considerate of municipalities, it does not confer additional jurisdiction on the Confederation. Essentially, this constitutional provision aims at fostering vertical cooperation between the three institutional levels of the Swiss federal structure but without bypassing the intermediary level, the cantons. The article refers specifically to the urban-rural divide and explicitly compels the national government to take account of the special priorities and needs of cities and urban areas on the one hand and mountain regions on the other hand. Among the concrete initiatives, the Tripartite Conference can be mentioned. It will be discussed at length further in the Country Report.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

As mentioned above, there are 26 systems of local government corresponding to the 26 Swiss cantons. Thus, there are considerable differences regarding the rules that apply to urban local governments (ULGs) and rural local governments (RLGs), etc. For example, the Canton of Zürich has granted a special status to the cities of Zürich and Winterthur. Most cantons, however, are based on a symmetric system and allocate the same tasks and responsibilities to all municipalities, irrespective of their size.

Despite of the wide variety of cantonal local government arrangements, some common features can be identified. Schmitt demonstrates that all municipalities are run by an executive council of five to ten members who are elected by the citizens and who are compelled to take decisions on a collegial basis.³ While they traditionally are not paid for their work, the elected members of municipalities’ councils in the ULGs tend to be professionals.

As regards legislative power, small municipalities (not to say RLGs) have citizens’ assemblies that meet regularly to pass new laws and/or to elect the executive council members and other authorities. On the contrary, some cantons have compelled larger municipalities (ULGs) to create a parliament, i.e. an elected legislative body *representing* the citizens. As Schmitt notes,

³ Schmitt, *Local Government in Switzerland*, above.

the Canton of Fribourg has adopted the Law on the Municipalities (*Loi sur les communes* in French) that requires eight specific municipalities to set up such a parliament while municipalities with over 600 inhabitants are only invited to do so.⁴ Smaller municipalities can keep their citizens' assemblies.

Finally, Schmitt puts a light on an interesting paradox: while municipalities still enjoy a large set of competencies and have the right to collect taxes (and set the tax rates), judicial power is not granted to the municipalities. In fact, the lowest judicial level is, in some cantons, the district's judge. Once again, one must look carefully at all the 26 cantonal organizations in order to grasp the subtleties of the local government systems that make Swiss federalism so complex.⁵

Political and Social Context in Switzerland

If the prominent role and the many responsibilities conferred to the municipalities have long been praised and recognized as a key factor for the success of the Swiss political model, one must note that they tend to lose their luster. In fact, the degree of autonomy enjoyed by the municipalities decreases due to the increasing requirements (land use planning, environmental protection, social aid, waste management, etc.) from the Confederation, the cantons and, to some extent, the people themselves. The democratic pressure (complexity of the legal frameworks, over technical policy fields, procedural overload, etc.) on the municipalities is difficult to manage, especially for non-professional elected representatives and somehow encourages the centralization of the decision-making power and the pooling of local tasks and duties at a superior level.

In the last 30 years, Switzerland has thus witnessed a strong acceleration of the number of amalgamations of its municipalities. From more than 3,200 municipalities in 1999, the number has dropped to approximately 2,200 municipalities in 2018. While the rural municipalities tend to merge, it can be observed that urban municipalities tend instead to agglomerate⁶ via different types of inter-municipal agreements. In any case, cantons and municipalities follow their own path with little interference from the national government. Today, approximately two thirds of the Swiss population is concentrated in the cities' centers⁷ or agglomerations.

⁴ *ibid.*

⁵ *ibid.*

⁶ According to the Federal Office of Statistics, the agglomeration can be defined as follows: An agglomeration is a group of municipalities with a total of more than 20,000 inhabitants (incl. overnight stays in converted hotels). It consists of a dense center and usually a crown. The delimitation of the crown is based on the intensity of the commuter flows.

⁷ According to the Federal Office of Statistics, the city-center can be defined as follows: The municipality which, among the central municipalities of an agglomeration, has the highest number of HENs (= sum of inhabitants, work places and overnight stays in converted hotels) is considered as a city-center. In some cases, it is possible for an agglomeration to have several central cities.

According to 2017 data, the 2,212 Swiss municipalities are relatively small, with 1,060 inhabitants on average, but very different in size. The smallest is Corippo with 12 permanent inhabitants and, like many others, spreads on less than 1 km². The largest in terms of territory is Scuol with 438.62 km² and the most populated is Zurich with 400,000 inhabitants. Many municipalities being unable to cope with the organizational requirements of today's life (school facilities, firefighter's service, water sanitation, etc.) and finding it difficult to recruit personnel, a strong process of merging local authorities has begun some sixty years ago and has accelerated in the last thirty years.

The four main coalition parties, namely the FDP. The Liberals, the Christian Democratic People's Party, the Social Democratic Party and the Swiss People's Party are all represented at the Federal level and in almost all the 26 cantons. Interestingly, in the urban cities, the traditional political parties are well organized and represented while in the smaller rural municipalities, political parties are less active. The peculiarity of small municipalities where every citizen knows each other means that people vote first for a specific candidate rather than for the parties.

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